

CO₂ electrocatalytic conversion: outlooks, pitfalls and scientific gaps

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ABSTRACT

CO₂RR electrocatalysis is a key technology/process for transformative (industrial) chemical production but requires accelerating the development of novel materials and approaches by turning the current design strategies. This contribution does not review this topic but instead highlights pitfalls and scientific gaps in the current approaches. The discussion is focused on electrode/reactor engineering and related aspects, including how to control the nano environment at the electrocatalyst surface. Their better understanding, especially the development of reliable modelling able to account for the complexity of the phenomena present in electrocatalysis, is the condition to accelerate the progress. It is also remarked that the mechanistic and design strategies used have an intrinsic methodological issue. Approaching catalysis from the perspective of selectively transferring energy for the activation barriers rather than only considering the nature of the active sites and the energetic pathways of transformation (the current approach) is discussed. The concept is related to the role of localised phonons, polarons and interaction with excitons in determining the CO₂ electrocatalytic conversion pathways.

Keywords

CO₂RR, CO₂ electrocatalysis, electrode and cell design, strategies for CO₂ electroconversion, localised phonons

Introduction

The electrocatalytic conversion of CO₂ (CO₂RR) is of increasing research attention. As an index, a search in SciFinder indicates an average of 50 per year reviews in English using as keywords "CO₂ and electro", about ten times higher than a decade ago. At the same, this poses the question of whether it could be necessary to have additional reviews on the topic. Looking more in detail at recent reviews highlighting the mechanistic and design aspects of electrocatalysts,¹⁻³⁷ it appears that despite the richness of indications and the undoubtful scientific advances, there is a lack of a generalised approach as the bases for the industrialisation of the process overcoming current limits (stability, Faradaic selectivity and specific current densities for reliable electrode sizes, above at least 10 cm²).

Industrial targets, even if dependent on the products, are current densities above 200 mA/cm² (better above 0.5 A/cm²) and Faradaic selectivities above 80-90% at high current densities. Other relevant aspects are the type of byproducts and how they impact downstream separation. At the same time, stability should be at least 1000h under variable loading. Other requisites are a nearly constant selectivity in an enough wide potential (at least 0.5 V) and current density range. Avoiding critical raw materials in developing the electrodes is also necessary. Purity and concentration of CO₂ are other key aspects of industrial scalability. The electrolyte choice or, preferably, its elimination are also critical issues, as commented later. Often, top-performance electrocatalysts were tested in unreliable conditions, and a drastic performance loss is observed when studies under conditions relevant to industrialisation. Thus, even if for some reactions (particularly the production of CO or ethylene), high current densities and Faradaic selectivities and efficiencies have been reported in the literature, as described in the cited reviews, the effective possible industrialisation is still far.

Overcoming this gap would require developing suitable strategies for CO₂RR. The focus in the literature has been mainly on catalyst design strategies. They include aspects such as

- i) surface morphology changes, for example, the control of the nanostructure, doping, defect engineering and formation of heterostructures, and modification by surface organic groups or molecular functionalisation;
- ii) development of specific active sites, such as single-atom catalysts (SAC) or dual-atom catalytic sites, facets engineering of nanoparticles, formation of bimetallic or core-shell nanoparticles, and generation of high-entropy alloys;
- iii) nano-architecture of the electrocatalysts, such as the development of dendritic nanostructures and rough surfaces, spatial confinement and hierarchical-porosity, generation of grain

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boundaries and mesostructural effects.

Typically, the design criteria are supported by theoretical modelling of the reaction mechanism and the nature of the active sites. However, often these insights are valid for the specific materials investigated, and there are several contradictions when generalised to the whole set of the electrocatalysts proposed to derive general trends in the electrocatalyst design. There are few comparative studies in this direction. One example regards the reaction of CO₂ electrocatalytic methanation.³⁸ Even limiting the analysis to a subset of relatively homogeneous electrocatalysts for which a detailed mechanistic approach has been proposed, there is an evident lack of general relations between reaction mechanisms, the nature of the active sites and catalytic performances.

This issue derives largely from the experimental observation of many authors that the surface microenvironment, type of electrode and operation conditions, cell design and other aspects not related to the electrocatalysts determine the performances in CO₂RR (selectivity, type of products, specific current density, side reaction of H₂ formation). These effects often predominate over the characteristics of the electrocatalyst itself.³⁹ Even unselective catalysts may become selective under proper conditions.⁴⁰ This and other shreds of evidence question the relevance of focusing on electrocatalysts only.

While attention is often given in the literature on aspects such as verification of the absence of products deriving by contamination (recommending, for example, tests with labelled CO₂), the need from an industrial perspective is rather on rigorous protocols of testing (including the use of reliable electrocatalytic cells and electrode sizes) which allow reproducibility of the results and understanding of their scalability. This question is far beyond the issue of contamination. Several literature results are largely not reproducible under conditions and reactors relevant from an industrial perspective.

On the other hand, CO₂RR is a key technology to address the carbon circularity and CO₂ reduction targets in energy-intensive industries⁴¹ It is part of the necessary processes to establish a new sustainable industrial chemical production not based on the use of fossil fuels as energy and C-source.⁴²⁻⁴⁴ There is a need to accelerate the development of industrial processes based on this technology to meet climate change targets.

The availability of renewable electrical energy to transform chemical production in this direction is often questioned. However, the same is valid for all emerging directions related to energy transition, from the production of green H₂ to electrical mobility. Chemical production is at the basis of an extensive value chain impacting all modern life. Investing in the decarbonisation of chemical production through electrification and closure of the carbon cycle would have a cascade

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effect on all the subsequent value-chain. Thus, the impact should not be measured as a direct amount of CO₂ recycled or fossil fuels avoided but as a global impact on the transformative economy. From this perspective, the low volume of chemicals with respect to fuels has minor relevance.

This comment remarks that the choice of the target products of CO₂RR also has to be viewed from this perspective, in addition to considering the integration of the technology in the value chain. Producing CO from CO₂ rather than other chemicals that involve a more complex transformation (ethylene production is a 12-electron reduction compared to a two-electron reduction in CO formation; in addition, a C-C coupling reaction is necessary) is easier and can be achieved with higher selectivity and energy efficiency. However, CO has to be further processes, which requires additional costs and energy. Suppose the final target is ethylene to have a straight comparison. In that case, H₂ must also be generated by electrolysis. Then CO and H₂ must be pressurised and catalytically transformed to ethylene, typically in a multistep process.^{45,46} Direct electrocatalytic production of ethylene, eventually in a two-step integrated electrocatalytic process (via intermediate CO further electrocatalytically converted to ethylene),⁴⁷ would be competitive over the hybrid electrocatalytic-heterogeneous catalysis approach. In addition, the electrocatalytic path is well-suitable for small-scale, decentralised production. It is more resilient than the hybrid process, avoids the cost and impact of transport, and better integrates with local resources. Thus, technological change has to be also considered from the perspective of changing the modality of production, which impacts the economics and environment in a far more complex way than accounted for by typical techno-economic estimations.⁴⁸

While the hybrid approach is currently at a higher TRL (Technology Readiness Level), it is necessary to accelerate the progress in direct electrocatalytic routes, similar to the case of producing H₂ by electrolysis and then using it to convert CO₂ by heterogeneous catalysis.^{49,50} The potential and selection of CO₂ electrocatalytic routes and technologies have to be assessed given the transformative scenario rather than using the traditional assessment criteria. This point is the challenge facing discussion on the future of electrocatalytic routes of CO₂ conversion, but instead, often not properly recognised. However, it is out of the scope to discuss these aspects further, being analysed in other contributions.^{42-44,49,50}

In addition, this contribution does not aim to be a further review of CO₂RR, which is already covered by many other reviews. Instead, it aims to highlight some less-covered aspects but relevant from the general perspective of fostering obtaining reliable results from the perspective of industrialisation of the technology.

The role of electrode and cell design

As commented in the introduction, design strategies in the literature focus mainly on the electrocatalyst itself. These strategies can be lumped into two main categories: those influencing the electronic nature of the active sites, and thus the energetic path of conversion, and those determining the density of the active sites, which influence current density, but also the selectivity (for the possibility of pairing reactions, for example). In other words, the mechanism and reaction pathways are often assumed to be independent of the electrocatalytic reactor design, engineering, and the choice of operative conditions. Many experimental results proved that this assumption is not valid.³⁹ While an intertwined relationship exists between electrocatalysts and electrode/reactor design, the latter often dominates the overall behaviour. The engineering of the electrode/reactor determines factors such as local pH around the active centres (and changes during the reaction), mass transport conditions and three-phase boundaries, e.g., the region at the interface between solid, liquid, and gas.⁵¹⁻⁵⁶

The theoretical mechanistic studies do not account for these aspects. In addition, a crucial missing element is that the potential at the electrocatalyst surface is not uniform, as typically assumed. A not uniform charge and potential distribution are rather present, depending on the nanostructure and electrode design. This fact determines gradient profiles in the electrodes beyond not uniform double layers, which generates not uniform electrolyte ions distributions, mass transfer, bubble generation and sticking, which sum to a non-uniform distribution in electrodes (particularly the porous ones) of the electrochemical active surface area (ESCA). Often what is interpreted as an electrocatalytic feature (for example, the exposed crystal facets in nanoparticles) is a modification of the potential distribution and related microenvironment. Thus, the effect observed depends on the latter aspect rather than to change in the electrocatalyst's electronic nature or geometry. However, these aspects are typically not even considered.

More aspects are discussed later. However, these brief comments prove that many of the mechanistic conclusions and strategies for CO₂RR are based on an oversimplification of the effective processes occurring. From this fact, they have limitations in developing effective strategies for improving CO₂RR.

The use of representative electrode sizes and reactor configurations

The presence of significant effects related to charge distribution and fluidodynamics of electrode-electrolyte interface remarks that testing with a minimum electrode size would be necessary to have reliable information on scalability and performance. In addition, the analytical

In: Zhang, G., Bogaerts, A., Ye, J., Liu, Cj. (eds) *Advances in CO₂ Utilization. Green Chemistry and Sustainable Technology*. Springer, Singapore. First Online: 28 March 2024

results' reliability also requires using electrodes with a minimum size. As an indicative value for CO₂RR testing, the electrode size should be at least 10 cm² using flow electrocatalytic reactors, as commented later. Several high-performance electrocatalysts reported in the literature do not meet these criteria, with the size of the electrodes often below 1 cm². Specific studies regarding the reproducibility and scalability of the results in the literature are missing. The practice is that valuable literature results are often not reproducible under conditions and reactors relevant to industrial scalability. Many aspects could determine irreproducibility and may raise endless questions out of the scope of this contribution. It is thus not relevant to analyse which specific results fail from this perspective but only advise the readers of care in using literature references and of the need to use reliable testing protocols.

Using suitable electrocatalytic reactors is also critical for the proper scalability and reliability of the results and mechanistic conclusions. The electrocatalytic tests are often made in an H-type cell, e.g., a cell with two liquid compartments separated by a membrane. The CO₂RR electrocatalyst acts as the working electrode in the cathodic chamber. The low solubility of CO₂ in aqueous media, the high availability of protons, the high electrolyte volume and the presence of often mass transfer limitations determine conditions at the surface of the electrode very different from those present under electrodes relevant for industrial exploitability that operate at high current density. Figure 1 illustrates this concept by presenting schematically the local concentration and pH gradients in conventional lab-scale reactors (H-type), gas-diffusion electrode (GDE) flow reactors and industrial conditions. The reactor, electrodes, and operative conditions can drastically change the availability of reactants at the surface and selectivity.

Figure 1. Effect of current density on the availability of protons, concentration of CO₂ and pH at the surface of a CO₂RR electrocatalyst. Reproduced with permission from ref. ³⁹ (Copyright Elsevier, 2023), reporting an elaboration of the indications given by Burdyny and Smith⁵⁷.

In: Zhang, G., Bogaerts, A., Ye, J., Liu, Cj. (eds) *Advances in CO₂ Utilization. Green Chemistry and Sustainable Technology*. Springer, Singapore. First Online: 28 March 2024

The optimal electrocatalysts should be different, being the micro-environment different. Thus, ranking in the H-cell may not give reliable results for industrial conditions. The behaviour in electrocatalysis is often dominated by the concentration of species at the catalyst surface and interface with the electrolyte rather than the electrocatalyst features. The dynamic of mass transport phenomena at a charged (porous) electrode and the dependence on the electrode and reactor design determine selectivity, onset potential and other aspects, which are instead typically ascribed to the intrinsic properties of the electrocatalyst. Understanding these comments better would require to discuss preliminary in more detail the type of electrodes and reactors used in CO₂RR testing.

Electrode

The simpler electrode is a planar metallic foil, which is unsuitable for CO₂RR. Many studies have proven the need to have size-controlled nanoparticles, which have thus to be supported over a conductive porous substrate such as carbon paper or mesh. However, to overcome limitations related to CO₂ solubility in the electrolyte, the use of gas-diffusion electrodes (GDEs) has become increasingly relevant. In this configuration, gas CO₂ is fed directly on one side of the electrode (typically treated with a hydrophobic substance such as Teflon to limit water back diffusion). It reaches the electrocatalyst localised on the other side of the electrode. The electrocatalyst could be in contact with the electrolyte or instead with the membrane, acting both as a separator of the cathodic and anodic zones and as a solid electrolyte. This configuration is indicated with different names (electroless, gas-phase, zero-gap electrodes). The latter is becoming the most popular.⁵⁸⁻⁶¹ Figure 2 illustrates schematically these electrodes.

Figure 2. Simplified drawing of planar, porous, gas-diffusion electrode (GDE) and zero-gap electrodes.

In: Zhang, G., Bogaerts, A., Ye, J., Liu, Cj. (eds) *Advances in CO₂ Utilization. Green Chemistry and Sustainable Technology*. Springer, Singapore. First Online: 28 March 2024

Planar or porous electrodes are the most used CO₂RR electrodes due to their easy manufacture.⁶² They operated immersed in a CO₂-saturated electrolyte, as outlined in Figure 2. Their performances strongly depend on the electrochemical cell design because their behaviour depends on CO₂ and ionic diffusion. For this reason, they cannot be used for high-current density tests. The porous electrode design with respect to the planar increases the active electrode area, reducing overall cell voltage at equivalent current density. While designing 3D-type porous electrodes, e.g., with higher thickness of the porous conductive substrate, could be a valuable way to increase the productivity per geometrical area of the electrode, the main issues to overcome are i) the intra-electrode mass transport, especially at high current densities, and ii) the inhomogeneities in electron distribution. While 3D-structured electrodes are desirable,⁶³ and new 3D-printing methods open new perspectives,⁶⁴ the main issues to overcome is understanding the complex multiphase flow in the pores, the interface interactions, and multiscale kinetics at the catalysts. Still, effective 3D electrodes for CO₂RR must be developed, even the recent interesting advances.⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷

The ohmic resistance of the 3D electrode depends on the nature and geometry of the substrate and the interfacial conductivity. A hierarchical morphology is necessary, which could be realised by functionalising metallic foams. Crucial aspects are the wettability and macroporous porosity because they affect the saturation/capillary-pressure relationship and, thus, the multiphase fluidodynamic inside the 3D electrodes.⁶⁸

While it is often considered that the electrode kinetics is dependent only on the electrocatalyst, the overall kinetics instead depend significantly on aspects such as the nature of the conductive substrate and interface with the electrocatalyst, the type of multiphase flows within the electrode and local environments. In heterogeneous catalysis, it is possible to measure the true kinetics and differentiate from the overall kinetics that heat and mass transfer limitations may influence. This approach is much more challenging in electrocatalysis. What is often considered depending on the electrocatalyst's intrinsic properties (for example, a change in the facets or defects in the electrocatalyst properties) is an indirect effect, e.g., there is an influence on nano environment and local hydrodynamics rather than on the intrinsic kinetic. In addition, a modification in the electrocatalyst nanoparticles could affect the interaction with the substrate and the resistance of electron transfer determining a change in the charge accumulation on the nanoparticles. This effect determines a change in the local potential and electron transfer rate. The change in the kinetic derives thus not from the presence of different active sites but from a change in the charge/potential distribution causing a change in the CO₂RR surface reaction rate and selectivity.

This example shows how often indirect effects determine the performances in electrocatalysis,

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rather than a change in the nature of the active sites and thus related considerations on the strategies for electrocatalyst design.⁶⁹ However, these aspects are typically not even considered. There are significant gaps, particularly in CO₂RR, in understanding aspects such as the relation between interfacial nano-architecture of the electrocatalyst/electrode catalysts and electrode kinetics. This is a major issue determining the lack of a general strategy in developing CO₂RR electrodes suitable for the industrialisation of the processes, as commented in the introduction. Electrocatalysis is far more complex than heterogeneous catalysis. Nevertheless, still, this complexity is not well understood. There is a tendency to consider electrocatalysis similar to heterogeneous catalysis and use similar approaches (for example, in modelling and mechanistic studies) while not recognising the intrinsic differences.^{38,70}

There are many additional issues. Due to the potential applied, an easier surface reconstruction and change may occur during electrocatalysis. Metal-oxides or hydroxide nanostructures may generate during CO₂RR, depending on the size and location of the nanoparticles.⁷¹⁻⁷³ They change the nature of the active sites, but at the same time, many other properties, from the wettability and nano environment to the change localisation, because they are poorly conductive.

GDEs typically show better CO₂RR behaviour with respect to planar and porous electrodes because the transfer rate of CO₂ to the electrode is enhanced.^{62,74} CO₂ diffuses directly through a gas-diffusion layer (GDL) to the electrocatalyst layer. The latter may be in contact with the electrolyte or the membrane separating cathodic and anodic zones, as outlined in Figure 2. Depending on various aspects, as commented later, the electrocatalyst layer can be located directly at the gas-liquid interface or fully wetted by the electrolyte. The last situation is apparently closer to porous configuration. However, in the GDE, the electrocatalyst, even if fully wetted, is still very close to the gas-electrolyte interface. The transfer rate is at least one order of magnitude larger.

Wettability and hydrophilic-hydrophobic characteristics of the electrocatalyst and GDE, catalyst loading, and porosity are among the key aspects determining the exact location of the electrolyte-CO₂ gas interface inside the GDL and with respect to the location of the electrocatalyst.⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶ The operative conditions and current density also influence this interface. Common GDLs are metal mesh/foam or a conductive porous macrostructured conductive carbon substrate (for example, carbon cloth or felt) treated typically by polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) to induce hydrophobicity. Structured GDLs (formed, for example, by macroporous/microporous layers) are common. The optimisation of GDE regarding porosity and electrolyte fluid dynamics is critical, even typically not made at a laboratory scale. Changes in these aspects (associated with changes in the electrocatalysts) may influence the observed CO₂RR performances often more than

the intrinsic changes in the electrocatalyst properties.⁶²

The optimised engineering of GDE should be made in parallel to that of the cell and operative

conditions, being these aspects strictly correlated. For example, Yang et al.⁷⁷ reported that the applied potential plays a central role in transitioning from a non-flooding to a flooding situation during CO₂RR, as summarised in Figure 3. This is also in relation to the size of the electrodes, being flooding easier at high current densities with respect to very small (below 1 cm²) electrodes. This issue is one of the aspects of why results using very small electrode sizes could not be reproduced with larger sizes or different cell configurations. However, these aspects are considered to a very limited extent in the literature and are part of the missing aspects determining reproducibility.

Figure 3. Simplified illustration of the transition from no-flooding to flooding conditions for GDE electrodes on increasing the potential and current densities. Revised from the indications given in ref.⁷⁷

The GDE electrode internal gradients and, consequently, the selectivity and product distribution in CO₂RR depends on the change in the fluidodynamics when turning from non-flooded to flooded conditions. Möller et al.⁷⁸ modelled the selectivity changes inside a GDE in a cathodic current range of 50–700 mA·cm⁻². Closer to the GDL side in contact with gas CO₂, the formation of C₂+ products (e.g., those with two or more carbon atoms) is favoured, while C₁ products form closer to the electrolyte side. A change in C₂/C₁ formation ratio occurs within the GDE due to the variation in the gradients. While many literature studies, supported by extensive theoretical modelling, remark on the need for specific characteristics of the electrocatalyst/active centres to produce C₂ rather than C₁ products in CO₂RR, these and other experimental and theoretical evidence,^{74,79-81} remark that the concentration profiles at the electrocatalyst (protons, CO₂, other ions present in the electrolytes)

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determine the path and selectivity in the transformation. The selectivity of CO₂RR is strongly influenced by the structure of the electrode and cell characteristics, which influence the effective gradients along the catalyst layer. In the zero-gap configurations (Figure 2), where the electrolyte is absent, the gradients are different, although specific literature studies are lacking.

There are also gradients in the local potential and current density along the electrode, which also determine changes in the reaction paths and selectivity. Kas et al.⁸¹ showed the presence of a spatial distribution of the current density and changes in local pH within the electrode. Large local variations in the current density ($>150 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) could be present. Nesbitt et al.⁵⁶ indicate the presence of different phase boundaries along the GDE profile and how high current-density CO₂RR performances could be obtained only by realising a high CO₂ diffusion. A change in the performances and selectivity may not depend on the electrocatalyst but only on how the electrode is realised, the presence of flooding aspects, the distribution of the electrocatalyst along the GDE, a variation in wettability and hydrodynamics, and other related aspects. Further aspects and an analysis of state of the art on the role of three-phase boundaries and interfaces in CO₂RR were discussed elsewhere.³⁹

Even if indications of these aspects are present in the literature, it is surprising that most mechanistic studies do not give proper attention to them. These studies indicate strategies of electrocatalyst design without verification on whether the variations observed could be interpreted differently, as commented in the introduction.

The message from the above discussion is that contrary to most of the literature studies in CO₂RR, the electrocatalyst design may often have a minor relevance with respect to other electrode/cell "engineering" aspects, even regarding reaction mechanisms and transformation paths. There is, thus, a difference and intrinsic higher complexity of the phenomena with respect to heterogeneous catalysis. However, most literature studies do not recognise this difference properly and tend to apply concepts and methodologies, including in modelling, valid for heterogeneous catalysis.

Electrocatalytic reactor and cell

In parallel to electrode design, optimising the electrocatalytic reactor and cell also has a marked influence on the performances and possibility of scaling up the results. As commented above, reactor and cell engineering are not an additional aspect to consider after defining the electrocatalyst and its performance. The ranking and selection of the electrocatalyst depend significantly on the choice of the reactor/cell, and the results may not be translatable to a different cell. The Faradaic

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efficiency and onset potential (associated with the electrocatalyst characteristics and typically assumed to be independent of the choice of the reactor/cell) depend instead on the reactor configuration and design. The reasons are the same discussed regarding electrode design, e.g., a behaviour highly dominated by the microenvironment rather than the nature of the electrocatalyst. Methodologies not accounting for these aspects, including theoretical methods, do not accurately describe the phenomena dominating the behaviour. From here, the lack of a generalised approach in CO₂RR electrocatalysis, as commented in the introduction.

Figure 4 reports a simplified overview of the main CO₂RR electrocatalytic reactors/cells. The H-type cell is the most used lab-scale CO₂RR reactor/cell. It is characterised by two containers containing the anode and cathode electrodes immersed in the electrolyte. The two containers are joined and separated using (optionally) a membrane to limit cross-over. In a review of some years ago, over 98% of literature studies on CO₂RR analysed (over 1100 papers) used H-type cells. Likely this percentage has decreased recently, but these reactors remain the most used in lab-scale and mechanistic studies. Weekes et al.⁸² recommended flow-type rather than H-type CO₂RR electrolyzers because the latter do not provide reliable data on the dynamic environment of an electrolyser.^{83,84} Even in an initial screening or for mechanistic studies, they may not provide the correct information.⁵⁷ Thus, even if the issue is documented, H-type cells continue to be used, and related results are utilised to propose design strategies for CO₂RR.

Figure 4. Simplified illustration of CO₂RR reactors/cells: H-type cell; GDE in a membrane-based flow cell, and advanced compact design for zero-gap flow cells with GDE on both anodic and cathodic sections. Notes: OER - oxygen reduction reaction; RE - reference electrode.

The zero-gap flow cell is preferable to perform tests at high current density and obtain reliable results for scaling the systems. Alinejad et al.⁶¹ evidenced how the same catalyst behaves differently

In: Zhang, G., Bogaerts, A., Ye, J., Liu, Cj. (eds) *Advances in CO₂ Utilization. Green Chemistry and Sustainable Technology*. Springer, Singapore. First Online: 28 March 2024

in H-type and zero-gap cells, in agreement with previous comments. An issue in zero-gap cells is the possible salt precipitation which affects stability, although strategies to mitigate the effect have been proposed.⁸⁵

The salt precipitation derives from the generation of hydroxide ions during the reaction, the use of high alkaline electrolytes, the formation of bicarbonate/carbonate ions by reaction with CO₂

and precipitation of potassium (bi)carbonate if KOH is used as the electrolyte. This process is illustrated in Figure 5 for reducing CO₂ to CO in a zero-gap cell using silver as the electrocatalyst.⁸⁵

Figure 5. Salt precipitation process in zero-gap CO₂ electrolysis. (a) Desired reactions and transport during CO₂ reduction. (b) Reduction of CO₂ producing CO and OH⁻. (c) Carbonation reaction: CO₂ reacts with the produced hydroxide ions. (d) Precipitation of potassium (bi)carbonate. (e) Precipitates

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accumulating in the gas diffusion electrode blocking pores. In the figure, oxygen is in red, carbon in black, hydrogen in white and potassium in petro colour. Reproduced with permission from ref.⁸⁵ Royal Chemical Society copyright, 2023.

The precipitation occurs at high electrolyte pH and high reaction rates. Although high pHs (up to 15) are used in several literature experiments to limit the side reaction of H₂ formation (HER - hydrogen evolution reaction) for many reasons (high conductivity and thus a high current density, reduced potential to apply, higher selectivity, particularly in ethylene production from CO₂),⁸⁶⁻⁸⁸ these conditions have to be discouraged from an industrial perspective.

The overall CO₂RR energy efficiency is strongly negatively affected by the reaction of CO₂ with OH⁻ to form carbonate because it causes CO₂ losses leading to a net negative energy balance when considering the regeneration of the electrolyte.⁸⁹ There is an apparent high energy efficiency because a high pH minimises cell voltage due to chemical potential and the dependence of the thermodynamic electrode potentials on the pH. However, the OH⁻ ions in the electrolyte are consumed by exergonic CO₃²⁻ formation. The energy required to regenerate CO₂ and 2 OH⁻ from aqueous CO₃²⁻ is larger than the energy stored by CO₂ electrolysis. A negative energy balance of around ~100–130 kJ·mol⁻¹ is present. Therefore, CO₂RR must be studied with electrolytes with a pH close to neutrality.

A comparative analysis of the three types of discussed electrocatalytic reactors is presented in Table 1. The focus is on aspects critical for the scalability and industrialisation of CO₂RR processes.

Table 1. A comparative analysis of the characteristics of H-type, GDE-based and zero-gap flow cells for CO₂RR. Note: ↑: good; ○: average; ↓: bad). Adapted from ref.³⁹ Elsevier copyright, 2023.

	<i>H-type cell</i>	<i>GDE-based flow cell</i>	<i>zero-gap flow cell</i>
Pressure drop	↑	○	↑
Current density	↓	○	↑
Uniform distribution of current	↓	○	↑
Gas handling	↓	↑	↑
Complex design	↑	○	↓

The zero-gap flow cell is the most promising configuration for obtaining high current density under an industrial scale. Typical current densities achieved in CO₂RR are 100–500 mA·cm⁻² range with a cell voltage of 2–5 V and energy efficiency of about 20–45%. Power, e.g., the energy required to

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run the system, is in the range of 0.1–10 W (per cm² of electrode surface area). As commented before, the size of the electrodes should be above about 10 cm². Although room temperature operations are typically investigated, higher temperatures, in the 50-70°C range, would often be preferable to improve the performances.

The zero-gap GDE electrolyser could be stacked as fuel cells and water electrolysers. Their costs are not significantly different from these better-established electrochemical applications, and they take advantage of the many technological developments made for the industrialisation of fuel cells and water electrolysers.

Beyond the current approaches in CO₂RR electrocatalysis

In heterogeneous catalysis, the behaviour is largely determined by the energetics of the chemisorption and transformation of reactants, intermediates and products on the solid catalyst. Theoretical methods determine the energy of the possible adsorbed species and indicate the lower energy path, e.g., having the lower activation energy for the limiting elementary step. These studies may be eventually integrated with supporting indications by a spectroscopic characterisation of the intermediates or indications from operando methods. In brief, this is the current approach in heterogeneous catalysis to establish the mechanism of the reaction and derive indications on the strategies to design improved catalysts. The same approach is also used for mechanistic studies in CO₂RR electrocatalysts, but several indications raise doubts about the effectiveness of this approach for electrocatalysis, as commented in the introduction. The difference between the two cases (conventional and electrocatalysts), besides the diverse temperature operation ranges, is the application of a potential and the presence of an electrolyte generating an electrical double layer at the interface. While it is obvious that these aspects would impact the mechanistic/kinetics of the reaction, it is surprising how scarce consideration is given to them in mechanistic CO₂RR studies.

As commented before, the electrolyte (concentration, species, buffer capacity, and pH value) influences the local reaction conditions impacting the pathways of CO₂ conversion. These and other aspects (electrode and reactor design, as indicated before) determine the mass transfer and availability of protons at the surface of the electrocatalysts, determining the rate of the side HER (hydrogen evolution reaction) and the transformation paths of CO₂, influencing both the nature and concentration of C-based intermediates. These aspects strongly correlate to electrode and reactor design because they influence the interface's local fluidodynamics. The previous section has given some examples. Many proofs in the literature exist of these aspects. However, the mechanistic studies on CO₂RR are largely based on approaches which not consider these aspects properly, for example, in DFT (Density Functional Theory) theoretical methods. Note that we do not intend to deny the contribution of theoretical methods to understanding catalysis but only remark that the current approaches cannot catch the complexity of electrocatalysis. Thus, new theoretical methods and approaches would be necessary. In contrast, indications using the current method do not provide enough reliable indications to develop a generalised design strategy for CO₂RR, which is necessary to progress towards the industrialisation of the technology, as commented in the introduction.

In electrocatalysis, differently from heterogeneous catalysis, applying a potential determines the generation of surface charges which can induce direct inner- or outer-sphere electron and/or energy transfer, thus not necessarily involving chemisorbed species. The electrical field at the surface

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determines a change in the structure of the electrolyte at the interface (the Stern layer), which strongly influences the rate of these processes (in classical Marcus theory of electrocatalysis, the rate of electron transfers depends on solvent reorganisation). In nanostructured electrocatalysts, the surface localised charges are not homogeneously distributed but depend on the nanostructure, even if few studies exist. A change in the nanostructure (for example, the nano shape of supported active metal nanoparticles) determines a change in the local electrical fields and charge distribution, which determines changes in the rate of electron/energy transfer. The change in the reaction rate of CO₂RR may be thus due to other reasons than a change in the exposed facts, as typically assumed.³⁸

A charged surface affects the mass transfer and chemisorption of species (CO₂, but also ions in the electrolyte and protons). Charged intermediate species (such as •CO₂⁻ anion radical formed by one electron transfer to CO₂) may diffuse back from the catalyst when a cathodic (negative) potential is applied. Diffusion and the local environment/pH strongly determine the path of transformation, with the presence of significant intra-electrode gradients, as earlier commented. These are some of the issues present in electrocatalysis, not present in heterogeneous catalysis, making the mechanistic studies complex and the application of simplified approaches unreliable.³⁸

Electrocatalysis requires a specific approach different from heterogeneous catalysis, while still, scarce recognition exists on this issue.⁹⁰ In addition to the presence of an applied potential and thus the presence of surface charges, the new open area is a non-uniform charge distribution at the electrocatalyst, depending strongly on the nanostructure of the electrocatalyst and electrode. The near-surface localised electrical field is a crucial aspect to consider, which induces a non-uniform double layer and near-surface electrolyte reorganisation, causing modifications in the surface adlayer and electrocatalyst reactivity and/or selectivity.⁹¹⁻⁹⁴

A disruptive model for approaching electrocatalysis

The above discussion remarked that the current approaches are not an acceptable description of complex phenomena occurring. In the modelling, it is necessary to consider the effect of the applied potential explicitly, the role of the electrolyte, the possible in-situ reconstructions during the electrocatalytic process, the low surface coverage or the presence of mass transfer limitations, the presence of gradients in concentration inside the electrode, a non-uniform distribution of the potentials and changes, the presence of an electrical field, etc.

It may also be advanced that even the fundamentals of catalysis for the design of electrocatalysts should be reconsidered. As commented before, DFT and analogous methods calculate the activation energies of individual reaction steps using a model surface. How to provide the energy necessary to

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overcome the activation energies of transition states is not considered because thermal energy provides sufficient energy to overcome the activation barrier at the operational temperatures of heterogeneous catalysts. This fact is one reason for a threshold temperature in heterogeneous catalytic reactions.

Due to the applied potential, the electrocatalytic reaction occurs at much lower temperatures than the equivalent reaction by heterogeneous catalysis. The conversion rate is usually negligible without applying external energy (the electrical potential). The energy that drives the process is associated with the potential that generates localised charges. It should be thus asked how the energy to the incoming or adsorbed molecule is transferred to overcome the activation barriers.

We suggested^{38,95,96} that the energy transfer involves surface phonons being the mechanism by which a solid can transfer energy to an adsorbed molecule.⁹⁷ A surface phonon is the quantum of a lattice vibration mode associated with a solid surface.⁹⁸ The energy transfer occurs by coupling the (localised) surface phonons with the molecule bond vibrations. Usually, surface phonons are extended vibrations, but when defects or nanostructures are present, they could be localised and have the energy to transfer to adsorbed molecules. It is thus analogous to the concept of active sites but translated into solid-state physics. Extended models based on Langevin dynamics can describe the phenomena.⁹⁹ This approach was never used to describe electrocatalytic processes and design strategies for their development.

Localised phonons, at a point and extended defects,¹⁰⁰ step edges, twin boundaries, etc., are necessary to transfer energy to the chemisorbed molecules selectively. There is a likely dependence on the nanostructure, even if this aspect was never investigated. It is evident, however, how the classical aspects related to the concept of the active site (in heterogeneous catalysis) could be translated in terms of factors breaking down the "propagating" modes of surface phonons localising them. In this way, there is a selective and effective energy transfer to the adsorbed molecule.¹⁰¹

Selectivity in energy transferring to the adsorbed molecule is the key to controlling the transformation pathway. Classical electrochemical theories or the current theoretical approaches do not account for this aspect. The design strategy is to tune the nature of the electrocatalyst to create localised surface phonons which match the energy required to overcome a specific activation barrier and drive the transformation along a specific path.

Furthermore, surface phonons interact with strong localised electrical fields and generate polaritons which have been suggested to play a relevant role in the transformative pathways of molecules whose high-frequency vibrational modes are strongly coupled with them (resonant catalysis).^{102,103}

In: Zhang, G., Bogaerts, A., Ye, J., Liu, Cj. (eds) *Advances in CO₂ Utilization. Green Chemistry and Sustainable Technology*. Springer, Singapore. First Online: 28 March 2024

When excitons (charges) are present, the coupling between excitons-phonons markedly influences the local electrical field and transfer rate to molecules.¹⁰⁴ Trapping of excitons by the lattice induces a strong electron-phonon coupling,¹⁰⁵ which could induce a multi-electron transfer in (electro)catalysis. In electrocatalysis, a simultaneous multi-electron transfer is important to provide a low-activation and overpotential path as in enzymatic mechanisms.^{70,106}

Scattered indications of these aspects are present in the literature. A theory to interpret the mechanisms of electrocatalysis in terms of localised phonons and modes to control them is absent. However, the above discussion offers thought for food for a disruptive interpretation of why current modelling approaches are ineffective in passing from conversion heterogeneous to electrocatalysis. They remark on the need for CO₂RR theoretical methods to address the mechanism to transfer the energy to chemisorbed molecules selectively. The same elements used to describe the active sites and related mechanisms could be used for an alternative mechanistic explanation.

Outlook/Future Perspectives

Electrocatalysis, specifically for the CO₂RR area, is a key technology/process for transformative (industrial) chemical production that meets climate change targets, sustainability and resilience. Even with the progress in the last years, it is necessary to accelerate the implementation of these technologies on an industrial scale. We advanced the idea that this acceleration requires developing novel materials and approaches by turning the current design strategies focused on the electrocatalysts, giving instead attention to electrode/reactor engineering and related aspects, including how to control the nano environment at the electrocatalyst surface.

We have shown that these aspects dominate the behaviour, including aspects typically related to electrocatalyst only, such as selectivity and onset potential. Their better understanding, especially the development of modelling able to account for the complexity of the phenomena present in electrocatalysis, is the condition to accelerate the progress. Current approaches are oversimplified. Consequently, the indications of the strategies for developing CO₂RR (industrial) processes are unreliable.

A key aspect remarked is that the current approaches in electrocatalysis derive from applying methods largely derived from heterogeneous catalysis. The mechanistic and design strategies used have an intrinsic methodological issue, which is not only related to a lack of analysis of what happens (in mechanistic terms) when a potential is applied. The existing approaches are not an acceptable simplification of the complex phenomena in electrocatalysis. We indicated some key aspects to consider that, even if challenging, are a necessary direction to explore.

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We also introduced the concept of approaching catalysis from the perspective of selectively transferring energy for the activation barriers rather than only considering the nature of the active sites and the energetic pathways of transformation (the current approach). The concept is related to the role of localised phonons, polarons and interaction with excitons in determining the CO₂ electrocatalytic conversion pathways. These species represent a solid-state alternative mechanistic interpretation of the active sites. Their role and how to selectively design the electrocatalysts and their nanostructure to make selective the energy transfer and thus control the path of transformation is a novel area of investigation which can be a breakthrough in understanding electrocatalysis and designing the next-generation electrocatalysis, overcoming current limitations.

In conclusion, CO₂ electrocatalytic conversion is a key technology for a sustainable future and carbon circularity. The outlooks are positive, but it is necessary to accelerate the progress in the area, particularly overcoming the current limits, due to an approach which is translated from heterogeneous catalysis rather than by properly understanding the critical elements characterising electrocatalysis. From here, the many pitfalls in literature, and the lack of reliability in a generalised approach to CO₂RR electrocatalysis, as commented.

There are thus many scientific gaps to overcome, some discussed in the paper, especially to develop strategies to design the electrocatalysts, electrodes and reactors/cells from an industrial perspective. They differ from the usually discussed aspects, such as scalability, purify of the feed, costs and technology maturity. These aspects are important but not the aim of the discussion in this contribution. Similarly, the aim was not to review state of the art and indicate the best electrocatalysts as a function of the target molecules. Many reviews are available on these aspects. We highlighted some less-covered aspects but relevant from the general perspective of analysing the effective impact of published results and derived indications on their reliability of the industrialisation of the technology. The aim is to evidence the general issues and missing aspects rather than a point-to-point analysis of the literature data, which may have a limited value.

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